

Curriculum Development for an OBE Approach Program with Specialization in Food Entrepreneurship

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ABSTRACT

"OBE is an approach to education in which decisions about the curriculum are driven by the exit learning outcomes that the students would display at the end of the course" (Davis, 2003) Entrepreneurial skills of student are related to the personal and interpersonal competencies, which are expressed in their behaviour. It is important to remember that entrepreneurial skills could not be achieved without training in business skills. The right combination of training and skills is the most effective factor to prepare and develop successful entrepreneurs (Osterbeek et al., 2010). It aimed to give a clearer picture on the statuses, planning, and management of students, as well as, the curriculum with the intention, to initiate an additional curriculum in the College of HRM. In this manner, they can apply theories learned inside the four walls of the classroom into practical undertakings into the real world. Through this initiative, the University of Cebu will be true to its vision to produce graduates who are industry leaders, thus, help give hope and transform lives of others. They will learn how to develop a business plan to organize their efforts and launch their business venture. The descriptive - survey method of research was used. The survey questionnaire was presented to the panel of examiners of Philippine Women's University (PWU) for critiquing. It was later pilot-tested to entrepreneurs of Talisay City, Cebu. The pilot-testing activity was help on April 15, 2014. Relationships of respondent's profile and entrepreneurial competencies based on their own experiences. Based on of respondent's profile and entrepreneurial competencies based on their own experiences. Based on the results of the study, the following can be concluded: The concepts of entrepreneurial competencies of HRM graduates plays a powerful construct for entrepreneurship education, training, and practice. No significant relationship existed between the respondent's demographic profile and their entrepreneurial competencies. The current curriculum of HRM should be reviewed and re-engineered to address the emerging needs of the region, as well as, in preparation for ASEAN 2015.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial competencies, HRM curriculum, ASEAN 2015

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

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Introduction

Food. It is a kind of a big deal. It's a fundamental part of life -- people eat! The kinds of food we served connect cultures and connect people. At the table, it brings people together to share a meal regardless of their background, beliefs, or language.

Entrepreneurial skills of students are related to the personal and interpersonal competencies, which are expressed in their behavior. These skills are not simply inherited from their parents. Sometimes, their belief would lead them to acquire such skills. It is important to remember that entrepreneurial skills could not be achieved without training in business skills. The right combination of training and skills is the most effective factor to prepare and develop successful entrepreneurs (Oosterbeek et al., 2010).

Entrepreneurship is a key driver of our economy. Majority of jobs are created by small and medium enterprises by entrepreneurially minded individuals. People who are exposed to entrepreneurship frequently express that they have more opportunity to exercise creative freedoms, higher self-esteem, and an overall greater sense of control over their lives. As a result, many experienced business people, economists, and educators believe that fostering a robust entrepreneurial culture will maximize individual and collective economic and social success on a local, national, and global scale. It is with this in mind that this study was proposed to be conducted in preparing the students to succeed in an entrepreneurial economy like the Philippines.

Business people and entrepreneurs have many similarities. They provide jobs for the unemployed, give solutions to the consumers, and help in developing the economy. However, they are not the same kind of people. A businessman can make a business out of an unoriginal business or product idea while an entrepreneur is an inventor and the first creator of the product. He invests time, energy and money on his idea.

Entrepreneurship as part of the Hotel and Restaurant Management (HRM) curriculum is a lifelong learning process, starting as early as elementary school and progressing through all levels of education, including adult education. The standards and their supporting performance indicators are a framework for teachers to use in building appropriate objectives, learning activities, and assessments for their target learners. Using this framework, students will have: progressively more challenging educational activities; experiences that will enable them to develop the insight needed to discover and create entrepreneurial opportunities; and the expertise to successfully start and manage their own businesses to take advantage of these opportunities (Van der Kuip and Verheul, 2004). This focuses on developing understanding and capacity for the pursuit, of entrepreneurial behaviors, skills and attributes in widely different contexts. It can be portrayed as open to all and not exclusively the domain of the high-flying growth-seeking HRM students. The inclination of these students to behave entrepreneurially is not exclusive to certain individuals. Different individuals will have a different mix of capabilities for demonstrating and acquiring entrepreneurial behaviors, skills and attributes. These behaviors can be practiced, developed and learned; hence it is important to expose all students to entrepreneurship education.

Entrepreneurial skills and attitudes of these HRM students in the University of Cebu provide benefits to society, even beyond their application to business activity. Factors such as personal qualities that are relevant to entrepreneurship, like

creativity and a spirit of initiative, can be useful to everyone, in their working responsibilities and their daily existence. The technical know-how and business skills of these HRM students need to be provided to those who choose to be self-employed or to start their business venture.

The researcher at the same time a faculty member teaching *Entrepreneurship* at the College of Hotel and Restaurant Management (HRM) of the University of Cebu opted to investigate the possibilities of adding one major in the HRM program that is BSHRM major in Food Entrepreneurship as an answer to the emerging needs in the region. The study was expected to give a clearer picture on the statuses, planning, and management of students, as well as, the curriculum with the intention, to initiate an additional curriculum in the College of HRM. In this manner, they can apply theories learned inside the four walls of the classroom undertakings, the real world. Through this initiative, the University of Cebu will be true to its vision to produce graduates who are industry leaders, thus help give hope and transform lives of others.

Background of the Study

Entrepreneurs are essential to the society because they build the economic engines that help the economy grow. They foster technological and social change, and their innovation and creativity forge the future. The University of Cebu – College of Hotel and Restaurant Management assists students in achieving their entrepreneurial goals. It is one of the many program's educational objectives of the College to produce graduates who have desires to venture into business in the hospitality services where their learnings can be best applied. The subject HRM 36 (Introduction to Entrepreneurship) combines class work, co-curricular activities and outreach programs that provide students with the opportunity to learn and practice entrepreneurship in a real environment. It offers a thorough and practical understanding of the issues involved in both starting a business and fostering innovation in a hospitality setting. The curriculum focuses on how the entrepreneurial process is applied in a variety of organizational contexts within and across national borders, ranging from new start-ups and rapid growth small firms to large corporations and nonprofits. Various perspectives on opportunity recognition and creative problem-solving are provided in an effort to help students capitalize on their entrepreneurial potential. Classes are taught using a combination of lectures, case studies, team exercises, guest speakers and fieldwork. Students can draw from a variety of carefully selected courses to become business generalists, well versed in organizing and managing resources.

HRM students who are enrolled in Entrepreneurship develop the skills necessary to identify a marketable product or service and to carry out the tasks required to get it to customers. They will learn how to develop a business plan to organize their efforts and launch their business venture. Entrepreneurship students are encouraged to start their ventures, work with a small or family business, or pursue entrepreneurial careers with major hotels and restaurants not only in Cebu but also in other parts of the globe.

Statement of the Problem

This study assessed the entrepreneurial competencies of graduates in the College of Hotel and Restaurant Management of the University of Cebu as basis for proposing an OBE curriculum in Food Entrepreneurship.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the entrepreneurs in terms of:
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 gender,
 - 1.3 educational qualification, and
 - 1.4 other trainings?
2. What competency standards can be established based on the experiences of successful entrepreneurs in terms of:
 - 2.1 leadership,
 - 2.2 innovativeness,
 - 2.3 technical,
 - 2.4 behavioral
3. What is the company profile of the entrepreneurs in terms of:
 - 3.1 type of business,
 - 3.2 product line,
 - 3.3 capitalization,
 - 3.4 years of operation, and
 - 3.5 number of employees?
4. Is there a significant relationship between profile of the entrepreneurs and their competency standards based on their experiences?
5. What is the rate of success of the entrepreneurs?
6. What entrepreneurial skills can be integrated in the curriculum by way of learning in the course enhancement?

Statement of Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant relationship between profile of the entrepreneurs and their competencies based on their experiences.

Significance of the Study

The study is expected to yield valuable information regarding the perceptions among students on barriers to entrepreneurship.

This study, therefore, will be of much help to the following:

Students. The output of the study will help students acquire the necessary skills to become food entrepreneurs since the modules are well designed to suit their needs for global competitiveness.

The University and the College of Hotel and Restaurant Management (HRM). The results of this study would provide the University the necessary information on new approaches in teaching. The College of HRM will be able to review the curriculum for the students to have quality education and to find more approaches that will showcase their talents and abilities.

Administrators. The findings and recommendations of the study may provide data needed to initiate and improve school co-curricular activities and faculty development program geared towards better achievement for the students.

Commission on Higher Education (CHED). This study will provide insights to CHED to come up with a seminar or symposium on entrepreneurship.

Faculty Members. Through this study, this would make them aware of the students' perceived contemporary issues on entrepreneurship and design a strategy that will benefit the students, the teacher, and the College.

Parents. The findings of the study would make them realize their role in the children's school performance. With the results of the study, the parents will be guided as to how they encourage their children to be aware on issues and problems in tourism and hospitality. They influence and control their children thus convincing them to develop positive attitudes.

Guidance Counselors. The findings of the study would enable them to design a student program regarding contemporary issues on entrepreneurship.

Researcher. The output of the study will serve as an instructional material in the teaching of Entrepreneurship among HRM students in the University of Cebu. The integration of the output in the course outline of Entrepreneurship is crucial since she has hands-on experience during the conduct of the study. Likewise, the experiential learning as a researcher could be best discussed in the four walls of the classroom than contemplating on textbooks alone. Thus, this will help her in her discussion, making it more reliable and effective to learners.

Future Researchers. Future researchers will benefit from the study, as it will serve as a guide and a source in conducting research studies related to the entrepreneurial skills of students.

Research Locale

The locale of this study were the food businesses in the Metropolitan Cebu owned and operated by the graduates of the different higher education institutions. These businesses include the following: brasserie and bistro, buffet and smorgasbord, café, cafeteria, coffeehouse, destination restaurant, Mongolian barbeque.

(Please see Appendix D for the map of Metropolitan Cebu)

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The sample was based on convenient sampling method. Hence, the findings might not be generalizable to the larger population. These findings were based on self-reported responses of the respondents. There may be biases, which could have affected the reliability of the results. This was a cross-sectional study; hence, causality analysis will not be discussed.

Definition of Terms

The following are the operational definitions of terms used in this study.

Competency. This refers to the necessary skills that students should acquire to make them ready and fit to work in the global arena. In this study, this refers to leadership, innovativeness, technical, and behavioral.

OBE Curriculum. This refers to the set of the detailed plan, activities, policies or courses that may be proposed to the College of HRM as a new curriculum that is, Food Entrepreneurship. This will provide a blueprint material needed by the students for them to acquire the necessary entrepreneurial skills and competence required in the hospitality management.

Entrepreneurial competencies. In this study, these refer to the respondents' leadership, innovativeness, technical and behavioral competencies. These are the wide range of competences that are seen useful to students. In this study, these include knowledge, skills and personal traits that students should possess.

Facilities. These refer to materials that store, prepare, package, serve, vend, or otherwise provide food for customers at the retail level, including the restaurant.

Perception. It refers to the score obtained by the respondents in the self-designed questionnaire. It may refer to the result of their observation and awareness of the elements of the environment through physical sensation.

Profile. The term refers to the respondents' attributes, such as, their company's details and their personal profile.

Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. This is a government agency that provides direction, policies, programs and standards towards quality technical education and skills development of students.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

The following literature and related studies provided relevant information and constructs which provided the framework to the present study.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Entrepreneurship is becoming increasingly important to strategic programmatic initiatives at universities. Entrepreneurship education at the university level is important to building the next generation of leaders for global innovation. The term entrepreneurship varies widely causing confusion when setting plans for entrepreneurship education curriculum development at the university level (Olsen and Mykletun, 2012).

Hidayat (2012) says that the university, including Hospitality Management Education plays a major role as home for faculty who innovates, takes calculated risks, and acts in a proactive manner. As the vehicle for economic and social change, Academic entrepreneurs in hospitality education are exploring opportunity, leveraging resources, creating change as its transformation. The creative entrepreneurial curriculum will bring positive impact to the process of transformation. It is the way in which entrepreneurship manifests itself to the body of hospitality education. Insight of the discussion is also defining stages of entrepreneurship curriculum implementation as well as identifying relevant competencies required to succeed the learning process.

Entrepreneurship education is a recent trend in new course development as against the traditional courses that have gained formal recognition in higher-level institutions. Entrepreneurship courses are now finding their way into formal education as subjects or full degree courses in the tertiary level. Unlike traditional business courses, which have developed and evolved over many decades in universities all over the world in conjunction with active practicing business operations, formal entrepreneurship teaching in the tertiary level is a relatively young course (Gatchalian, 2010). Entrepreneurship is an essential drive that keeps the economy sustainable. As the higher education is becoming more and more popular, people attach more importance to entrepreneurship education. The goal of entrepreneurship education is to develop the student's entrepreneurial spirit and cultivate knowledge and skill (Ping-ping et al., 2005). Nwekeaku (2013) says that though many Nigerian

universities have embraced the entrepreneurship education, there is not yet any fundamental change in the teaching and learning process. Most of the lecturers have not acquired new and special skills, the teaching methodology has not fundamentally changed from the old system, adequate and appropriate equipment are yet to be procured, the value system which favors certificate acquisition in preference to practical demonstration and ability is still in vogue, the general attitude of the society which favors craze for immediate materialism to functional education is still subsisting. An immediate review of the entrepreneurship curriculum for result oriented skills and functionalism, provision of necessary learning materials and equipment, regular training and retraining of lecturers, orientation for a new and desired value system, improved funding, among other measures, are recommended for a functional entrepreneurial education in Nigerian universities.

Entrepreneurship educators teach in and introduce new frontiers where they discuss teaching entrepreneurship as a method. The method is a way of thinking and acting, built on a set of assumptions using a portfolio of techniques to create. It goes beyond understanding, knowing, and talking and requires using, applying, and acting. At the core of the method is the ability for students to practice entrepreneurship and introduce a portfolio of practice-based pedagogies. These include starting businesses as coursework, serious games and simulations, design-based thinking, and reflective practice (Neck and Greene, 2011). Despite the recognition that education and prior entrepreneurial experiences influence people's attitudes towards starting their own business, the impact of entrepreneurship or enterprise education, as distinct from general education, on attitudes or perceptions of entrepreneurship has remained relatively untested. University-based entrepreneurship curricula have attracted the bulk of research within the area of entrepreneurship education leaving a gap pertaining to pre-university entrepreneurship and enterprise programs. However, entrepreneurship development in primary and secondary schools has received growing attention because students have expressed a desire to participate in entrepreneurship education programs. It is believed that the ideal stage to acquire basic knowledge about entrepreneurship and to foster a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship is during childhood and adolescence years (Peterman and Kennedy, 2003). School curriculum is responsive to the society, reflecting the needs and aspirations of its learners. A curriculum does not exist in isolation. It is an outcome of varying degree of mutual interaction between variables such as different learning styles of students, teacher and teacher preparation, evaluation practices, instructional and illustrative material and research (Vaidya, 2014).

Entrepreneurship as behavior, skill and an attitude requires an enabling environment for its integration with various scholastic subjects that are, language learning, social science, science and mathematics. Given the multi-dimensional nature of entrepreneurship, there is a need to plan a methodological framework about the content and form for cross-curricular learning and integration. Bringing entrepreneurship in the school curriculum and its progression, require substantial understanding about educational objectives, context, pedagogy and assessment (Ibid, 2014).

Food entrepreneurs perform many tasks. In addition to being a good cook, one must be able to obtain funds, hire workers, choose location and decors, obtain food supplies at a reasonable cost, and market the restaurant (Lazear, 2004). The results of the study of Gellynck et al. (2007) demonstrate that internationally

operating firms benefit from regional networking. It is argued that regional networking is not contradictory to an international market orientation, and that firms gain innovation competence by searching for external knowledge on different geographical scales. As these networks have the potential to enhance the innovation competence of firms, support to regional networking is promoted as a policy tool. Street vending is a prevailing and distinctive part of a large informal sector in Dhaka city, the capital of Bangladesh. The problem areas are related to business operation, business knowledge, extortion, and product and production. Through regression analysis, it has been found that business experience, and initial capital are two key factors that positively affect sales revenue. Formal education, however, does not have any significant impact on business performance (Muzaffar, Huq and Mallik, 2009).

Frank (2007) addresses what entrepreneurship skills and attitudes could contribute to the profile of the profession and whether it would be valuable to include such skills in the planning curriculum. The study concludes with potential advantages and disadvantages of incorporating subject specific entrepreneurial skills in planning curricula and proposes some approaches for teaching enterprise and entrepreneurship skills.

Entrepreneurship is the key to a successful global economy. This provides a framework for understanding, background information, defining differences between managers and entrepreneurs, strategies and ways to export and expand entrepreneurship globally (Schramm, 2006). Higher educational institutions (HEIs) should develop more flexible approaches with the focus on different groups of students in accordance with their various educational backgrounds. In response to the change of graduate labor market and the quest for sustainability, HEIs have to integrate the change of mindset, skills and abilities about entrepreneurship in their general academic education in order to nurture university students' entrepreneurial intentions (Wu and Wu, 2008).

Kirby (2004) examines the characteristics and role of the entrepreneur and the challenges for business schools posed by the need to develop more enterprising individuals, the argument is the traditional education system stultifies rather than develops the requisite attributes and skills to produce entrepreneurs, and proposes that if entrepreneurs are to be developed, considerable changes are required in both the content and process of learning. The study suggests that there need to be a shift in the emphasis from educating "about" entrepreneurship to educating "for" it. It stresses that entrepreneurship should not be equated with new venture creation or small business management, but with creativity and change. Educational institutions need to change the process of learning to enable their students to develop their entrepreneurial capabilities so as to encourage and stimulate the entrepreneurial imagination. Heinonen and Poikkijoki (2006) provide information on their study on entrepreneurship emphasizing the core role of opportunity – discovering, evaluating and exploiting it – and reviews teaching techniques currently used in entrepreneurship education. The entrepreneurial-directed approach seems to be well suited to the teaching situation as it encourages students to broaden their perspectives, and also to develop the entrepreneurial skills and behavior.

Oosterbeek et al. (2010) analyze the impact of the leading entrepreneurship education program on college students' entrepreneurship skills and motivation using an instrumental variables approach in a difference-in-differences framework. They

exploited the program offered to students at one location of the school but not at another location of the same school. Louw et al. (2003) say that development in the global and national economies, as well as, the labor market have made it necessary that more attention be paid to entrepreneurship and the updating of curricula presented by tertiary institutions. The study revealed that the levels of students' entrepreneurial traits have to establish whether these are interrelated and that they have to determine the extent of the impact of demographic variables on these entrepreneurial traits.

The results of the study of Matlay (2008) indicate that the student needs for entrepreneurship education does not match actual outcomes in terms of entrepreneurial skills, knowledge and attitudes. This mismatch influences an entrepreneur's perceptions of actual and future educational needs. Most of the student entrepreneurs, however, seem to be satisfied with the outcomes of their entrepreneurship education, both in relative and absolute terms. The findings provide valuable insights for educators, policy makers and entrepreneurs. Stakeholders could use this study to make better choices in relation to the education of future entrepreneurs. Barron (2008) investigated the nature of hospitality employment among new recruits in the hospitality industry and reports on thoughts of soon to graduate hospitality students. It discussed contemporary attitudes toward the generation undertaking hospitality education and making career decisions and considered the current generation's specific attitudes toward education and careers and the potential consequences this will have for the hospitality industry in the future. It argued that educators require to be more fully aware of the consequences of reducing the practical and vocational nature of programmes and that adjustments to the management and administration of programmes are essential to allow students to complete programmes.

Chen (2007) says that new venture's innovative capability is influenced by the interaction of the lead entrepreneur's leadership and the entrepreneurial team members' creativity, as measured by the creation of patents. New venture's innovative capability can be improved by the joint contribution of higher entrepreneurial leadership and more creativity in entrepreneurial teams. Investment in new, different, long-term work-related learning arrangements than have been undertaken hitherto is a high priority. Workplace learning for entrepreneurs in the context of lifelong learning should take place in settings where new knowledge is constructed in dialogue with the entrepreneurs' environment and where experts in learning facilitate personal competence development (Lans et al., 2004).

Badeaux (2013), says economic factors play an immense part in the survival and success of restaurants. Restaurants are partly dependent on the availability of disposable income of families or individuals and that, economic factors play immense part in the survival and success of restaurants. Restaurants are partly dependent on the availability of disposable income of families or individuals. The results of the study of Bhaskaran (2006) indicate that incremental innovation offers substantial competitive advantages to small and medium-sized firms, that incremental innovations can be adopted and operationalized rapidly by entrepreneurs with different cultural backgrounds and skills, and that small and medium-sized firms that focus on sales and marketing innovations are profitable and are able to compete successfully with large businesses. Beugelsdijk (2007) empirically studied the relationship between entrepreneurial culture and economic growth. Extensive

robustness analysis suggests that differences in economic growth in Europe can be explained by differences in an entrepreneurial culture, albeit mostly in an indirect way.

Entrepreneurs' innovativeness and personality play a key role in the adoption of innovations in small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Following two complementary approaches, this study conceptualizes innovativeness at two levels of abstraction: general innovativeness (GI), that is, the degree of openness to newness; and specific innovativeness (SI), that is, the predisposition to be among the firsts to adopt innovations in a specific domain (Marcati, Guido and Peluso, 2008). Entrepreneurs engender relatively much employment creation, productivity growth and produce and commercialize high-quality innovations. They are more satisfied than employees. However, the counterparts cannot be missed either as they account for a relatively high value of GDP, a less volatile and more secure labor market, higher paid jobs and a greater number of innovations and they have a more active role in the adoption of innovations (Van Praag and Versloot, 2007).

The study of Utsch and Rauch (2000) aims to extend earlier research and to test a model in which innovativeness and initiative are mediators between achievement orientation (including the psychological characteristics: self-efficacy, higher order need strength, need achievement, and internal locus of control) and venture performance. The results suggest that innovativeness is a mediator between achievement orientation and venture performance, whereas initiative could not be confirmed as a mediator. The role of personality traits in the decision to start a business and to maintain it successfully is discussed controversially in entrepreneurship. The results indicate that traits matched to the task of running a business produced higher effect sizes with business creation than traits that were not matched to the task of running an enterprise. The traits matched to entrepreneurship significantly correlated with entrepreneurial behavior (business creation, business success) need for achievement, generalized self-efficacy, innovativeness, stress tolerance, need for autonomy, and proactive personality. These relationships were of moderate size in general and, moreover, heterogeneity suggested that future research should analyze moderator variables (Rauch and Frese, 2007).

It is clear that an innovation was regarded as essential by most small food firms. Such firms tended to introduce new products continuously, develop new of innovation depending on the age of the company, company size and regional economic performance (Avermaete et al., 2003). Salavou and Lioukas (2003) investigate whether market focus, technological posture and entrepreneurial orientation lead to the adoption of more radical product innovations. Empirical results appear to support the claim that it is mainly entrepreneurial orientation that favors the choice of radical product innovations. This suggests that in SMEs the notion of entrepreneurial-push outweighs both market-pull and technology-push arguments.

Today's innovation process integrates more sophisticated market, and a post-audit is carried out after the new food concept has been launched. In comparison, studies of Michelin-starred chefs development teams use an approach that is much more explicitly structured as a whole due to the larger scale roll-out, as well as, greater cross-functional and regional differences to consider in the setting (Ottenbacher & Harrington, 2009). Chang et al. (2011) investigate how hospitality companies can promote incremental and radical innovation through human resource management practices. The two human resource management practices are also

found to have a negative joint impact on incremental but not radical innovation. The importance of innovation as the key driver of sustained success has been well documented in the marketing and hospitality literature. In the past decade, several studies have investigated the success factors associated with service innovations. Few of these studies, however, have dealt with hospitality innovations. Hospitality firms develop innovations with specific objectives and goals in mind and have several approaches to measuring performance accordingly (Ottenbacher, 2007).

Innovation in food service technology offers differentiation and cost leadership in strategic terms. Majority of food service businesses do not have research and development laboratories. At present, the innovations in equipment design and layout, packaging and service techniques are defensive or reactive in nature. Examples of defensive innovation include faster and better preparation methods, improved temperature control, even heating, energy and labor savings, less waste, better sanitation, faster service and flexibility. In contrast, developments in offensive or pro-active innovation, which can radically change current practices, are rare. Novel food service processes can evolve as a result of an adoption of technological breakthroughs in "high tech" fields of the economy. This justifies investments in offensive research and highlights the importance of technical competencies for a food service professional (Rodgers, 2007).

This study develops a conceptual scheme of development and realization of the strategy of innovation development in a restaurant. It experimentally confirms the hypothesis of availability of a very strong density of the feedback between resistance to innovation changes and a variable share of qualified personnel that is capable of permanent development (learning) and generation of new ideas, in restaurants and builds a model of dependency between them. The prospects of further studies in this direction could become scientific studies directed at development of methodical approaches to identification of the level of innovation potential and assessment of efficiency of managing innovation development of different (by type, class, size) restaurants. The obtained data could also be used for development of a new or improvement of the existing tools of strategic management of innovation development at the micro-level (Naidiuk, 2013).

Marsili (2002) examines the sources and obstacles to entrepreneurial entry related to the process of technical change. He said that opportunities for entrepreneurship are shaped by the nature of knowledge underlying different technologies. These points are illustrated using U.S. patent statistics classified by technical field and sector of firm's principal product activity. Sustainable entrepreneurs, i.e. those who proactively facilitate latent demands for sustainable development, are now in higher demand than ever before. Higher (business) education can play an important role in laying the foundation for these sustainable entrepreneurs. Traditionally, however, educational scholars focus either on the issue of education for sustainability or on entrepreneurship education. There is little work that explores and/or crosses the boundaries between these two disciplines, let alone work in which an effort is made to integrate these perspectives. A competence approach was taken as a first step to link the worlds of education for entrepreneurship and for sustainability because we postulate that both, apparently different, worlds can reinforce each other (Lans, Blok and Wesselink, 2014).

New product development is virtually established as the most viable tool for long-term corporate growth if properly managed. Design to evaluate the planning and

management of new food product development in the food industry (Ilori, Oke and Sanni, 2000). Entrepreneurial studies are interdisciplinary training that focuses on the tools needed to start a new business or vocation. This is fast becoming a predominantly youthful society with the high rate of unemployment requires training the youth in entrepreneurial skills to tackle the unemployment, which has reached alarming proportions (Maigida, Saba and Namkere, 2013).

An important assumption of entrepreneurial competence is that it can be learned and developed. However, human resources development practices aimed at further strengthening and developing small-business owner-managers' entrepreneurial competence is complex and underdeveloped (Lans et al., 2010). Drawing on the concepts of 'entrepreneurial' and 'dynamic' capabilities, this study examines the capabilities that allow small firms to operate as suppliers to large organizations in the public and private sectors. Interest in this topic is fuelled by academic speculation about the extent to which such supply chain relationships can facilitate the growth of small firms and by current policy initiatives to promote small firm-friendly procurement practices (Woldesenbet, Ram and Jones, 2012). Sambasivan et al. (2009) studied the role of personal qualities, management skills, and opportunity recognition skills of entrepreneurs in influencing the venture performance. In this study, personal qualities and management skills were combined into a single construct, qualities-skills. The results indicated the following: opportunity recognition skills acted as a "pure" mediator, opportunity recognition skills influenced the venture performance, alertness mediated the relationship between personal qualities and venture performance, and alertness and prior knowledge mediated the relationship between management skills and venture performance. Sales volume, sales growth, and stability in profit were used as measures of venture performance.

Entrepreneurial attitude instilled in active entrepreneurs as compared with passive entrepreneurs is primarily mirrored in new products, which embody in their characteristics higher uniqueness; an ingredient found to act as an important contributor to product performance (Avlonitis and Salavou, 2007). The education and training for the entrepreneur can be considered from a behavioral perspective, with an emphasis on behavioral modification of the entrepreneur's learning patterns rather than skill or knowledge acquisition only. Also, this should be grounded upon the provision of appropriate contexts that provide or simulate the experiences of which the entrepreneur will likely come across, so that the learning behaviors can be stimulated (Man, 2006).

Results of the study conducted by Leikas et al. (2007) showed that food risk perceptions generally form two dimensions; scariness and likelihood, but that this may depend on the nature of the risk. In addition, results imply that individuals with high avoidance motivation perceive food risks as scarier and more likely than others, and that individuals with an analytic information processing style perceive food risks as less likely than others. Trait anxiety seems to be associated with higher food risk perceptions only among men.

The community of social entrepreneurs should benefit from knowing what really does and does not work when creating social value through a for-profit firm. For this analysis, a social venture is one that seeks to effect social and environmental change through a business; from its beginning, it intends to create social or

environmental value for other stakeholders, in addition to making a profit. These ventures can define their actual or potential social impact in concrete ways (Clark and Ucak, 2006). Entrepreneurship and innovativeness have seen considerable attention in the literature. However, little research has focused on micro-scaled enterprises, especially in the context of nature-based tourism. This investigates how entrepreneurial attitude influences innovativeness and performance in Norwegian nature-based tourism enterprises. Respondents that exhibit a stronger entrepreneurial attitude appear more likely to change the way they organize their enterprise and tend to have higher income growth. Results point to potential policy actions that could positively impact rural development as well as individual firm actions that may enhance performance (Nybakk and Hansen, 2008).

Elston & Audretsch (2011) examine the role of personal capital in the entry decision for US high-technology entrepreneurs. Wealth appears to have a positive impact on the probability of starting up a firm, even when controlling for risk attitudes; however, risk attitudes do not appear to have a strong role to play in the entry decision overall. Policy implications suggest that firm start-ups are dependent on access to capital in both initial and early stages of development, and that government funding is an important source of capital for potential and nascent high-technology entrepreneurs. As the vehicle for economic and social change, academic entrepreneurs in hospitality education are exploring opportunity, leveraging resources, creating change as its transformation. The creative entrepreneurial curriculum will bring positive impact to the process of the above transformation. It is the way that entrepreneurship manifests itself to the body of hospitality education. Insight of the discussion is also defining stages of entrepreneurship curriculum implementation as well as identifying relevant competencies required succeeding the learning process. The result shows that entrepreneurship stakeholders can use the findings of the study to implement and improve curriculum design, delivery methods and assessment strategies in their efforts to advance entrepreneurship in hospitality management education (Hidayat, 2012).

The study of Gurel et al. (2010) investigates the relationship between entrepreneurial traits, socio-cultural background and entrepreneurial intention of university students in the UK and Turkey. The findings indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between innovation, propensity to take risks, entrepreneurial family and entrepreneurial intention. Education does not seem to play an important role in fostering entrepreneurial traits and intentions of university students. Morrison & Johnston (2003) say that systematic approaches to the development of creativity amongst higher education students appear to be limited. The consequence is that prospective lecturers and students find themselves with little practical guidance to action. The study concluded that creativity could usefully be introduced into the curriculum more systematically and widely and with greater coherence, rather than being ring-fenced into a stand-alone class.

The study of Cheng et al. (2009) concerns students' perceptions towards the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education in their respective institutions. The results are limited in terms of their ability to demonstrate actual outcomes of entrepreneurship education. This provides an important exploratory analysis of the state of entrepreneurship education in Malaysia to enable further research to be taken in the area of entrepreneurship education. The findings provide valuable insight on effective teaching methodologies in the area of entrepreneurship

education. Gatchalian (2010) identifies the training needs of entrepreneurship educators and practices in entrepreneurship education in the Philippines. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and one-on-one interviews are conducted using structured and unstructured interview guides, which revealed the respondents' answers, thought patterns, expressions and insights on an array of questions pertaining to entrepreneurship education in the Philippines. The result shows that students assign the highest importance to the personal qualities of entrepreneurship educators and teaching methodology and delivery among other qualities (e.g. educational attainment). Entrepreneurship educators ascribe most importance on personalized, experience and project-based learning. However, they assert that this teaching practice should be complemented by a manageable class size, program support facilities and teaching skills enhancement among others. The school administrators play an important role in setting the direction and progression of the entrepreneurship program in their respective institutions against the background of numerous challenges in managing resources to support its needs. This study highlights that entrepreneurship education in tertiary level is best achieved through a well-designed curriculum, effective teaching model grounded on personalized and experience-based learning, and strong institutional support.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1 shows the research paradigm of the study.

Figure 1. The Research Paradigm

As presented in figure 1, the inputs of the study were the profiles of the company and the entrepreneurs, and competency standards as experienced by the successful entrepreneurs.

After identifying the input variables, the data were gathered using validated survey questionnaires, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using some statistical tools. A proposal for an OBE curriculum for Food Entrepreneurship was drafted for the College of HRM to consider in the development of its curriculum.

The researcher gained more insights from these theorists and researchers in the conduct of the study. These insights include the methods, factors, and variables that are interrelated to each other and are relevant in the formulation of this research. It has motivated the researcher to conduct this study and propose an outcomes-based curriculum for the Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management major in Food Entrepreneurship of the University of Cebu, Cebu City.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research participants, its environment, instruments, and the statistical tools that were used in the treatment of the data.

Research Design

In this study, the descriptive – survey method of research was used. This involved the collection of data through the use of questionnaires and informal interviews, which were used as inputs in determining and analyzing the present curriculum and instructional materials in Entrepreneurship.

Research Participants and Sampling Method

The research participants were the graduates of Associate and Baccalaureate degrees in Hotel and Restaurant Management of the University of Cebu. In this study, fifty food entrepreneurs were used as participants using purposive-random sampling with the following as the inclusion criteria: graduates who are food entrepreneurs by choice or by inheritance from their family who owned food businesses in Metropolitan Cebu. Some of them learn how to manage their business through their parents.

Research Instrumentation

A researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather data on the profiling and entrepreneurial competency of the respondents. An interview guide questionnaire was also used for follow-up and validate the respondents' response on the questionnaire. The survey-questionnaire was to the panel of examiners of Philippine Women's University (PWU) for critiquing. It then underwent reliability testing to ensure the validity of the questionnaire. The test got a Cronbach alpha of 0.9587, which means that the questionnaire was considered Highly Reliable. It was later pilot-tested to ten food entrepreneurs of Talisay City, Cebu. The pilot-testing activity was held on April 15, 2014. Please see appendix E for the pilot-testing results using Minitab 17.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following preliminary preparations were done to make sure that the gathered data are valid. A transmittal letters addressed to the respondents was prepared which were personally handed-in to the respondents for administration. The researcher distributed the questionnaire to all respondents selected using purposive sampling. After the problems had been identified, surveys related to entrepreneurial competencies were then gathered and analyzed. Finally, the data were collected, tabulated, analyzed and statistically interpreted. The questionnaire had three parts. The first part of the questionnaire is on the profile of the entrepreneurs. This part contained data such as age, gender, educational qualification, and other trainings. The second part of the questionnaire dealt on the competency or account of the experiences of successful entrepreneurs. This part was a self-assessment questionnaire, consisted of four components, namely: leadership, innovativeness, technical, and behavioral, wherein the respondents were advised to encircle their responses on the extent of usefulness of each of the indicators based on their experience as entrepreneur. The third part of the questionnaire as the company profile of the entrepreneurs which included the type of business, product line, capitalization, years of operation, and the number of employees.

Statistical Treatment

The following 3 - point liker scale was used to rate the extent of the usefulness of the respondents entrepreneurial skills. Scale, Mean Range, Verbal Interpretation and Interpretation.

The following statistical tools were used in the treatment of data:

Pearson r. Was used to test the relationship of the profiles of the entrepreneurs and their competency standards based on their experiences as successful food entrepreneurs.

Percentage. Was used in the presentation of the profile both the company and the respondents.

Rank. Was used in the presentation of multiple response data of the respondents' profile specifically the training needs.

t-test. This formula was used to test the significance of correlation r.

Weighted Mean. Was used to analyze the entrepreneurial competency standard on the extent of the usefulness of the entrepreneurial skills.

- 3 - Very Useful (VU) - The indicator is very worthwhile for entrepreneur.
- 2 - Moderately Useful (MU) - The indicator is somehow worthwhile for entrepreneur.
- 1 - Least Useful (LU) - The indicator is a bit worthwhile for entrepreneur.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Evaluation is a systematic determination of the study's merit, worth and significance, using criteria governed by a set of standards. It can assist businesses to assess any aim and the realizable concept to help in decision-making in regard to the aim and objectives and results of any such action that has been completed. This section, therefore presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered from the respondents of the food businesses in the Metropolitan Cebu during Summer 2014.

Profile of the Entrepreneurs

Table 1 presents the profile of the entrepreneurs in terms of age, gender, educational qualification, college graduated, and other trainings. Not all food

entrepreneurs are graduates of hospitality management. Some of them are graduates of business and management, nursing, and information technology.

Table 1
Profile of the Entrepreneurs

Age (in years)	f	%
18 to 25	5	10.00
26 to 31	9	18.00
More than 32	36	72.00
Total	50	100
Mean = 43.02		
Standard deviation = 12.41		
Gender	f	%
Male	18	36.00
Female	32	64.00
Total	50	100
Highest educational attainment	f	%
Baccalaureate degree holder	44	88.00
Master degree holder	6	12.00
Total	50	100
Trainings attended	f	Rank
Food safety	20	1
Food and water microbiology	17	2
Food labeling	11	3.5
Sanitation standard operating procedures	11	3.5
Safety and risk assessment	9	5
Food safety laws and regulations	8	7
Food safety management system	8	7
Good hygienic practices	8	7
Chemical and physical hazards in foods	7	9
Epidemiology and surveillance of Foodborne diseases	6	11
Food defense	6	11
Hazard analysis critical control point	6	11
Sanitary and phytosanitary measures	5	13
Good manufacturing practices	4	14
Major parasites causing Foodborne diseases	3	15
Good agricultural/aquaculture/animal husbandry practices	2	16
Stored product pests	1	17
Total	50	100

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents' were 32 years old and older, female, baccalaureate degree holder in both business and management or hotel and restaurant management. Looking closely at the table, it further records that entrepreneurs attended the training on food safety, food and water microbiology, food labeling, sanitation standard operating procedures, safety and risk assessment, and food safety and law procedures.

Data in Table 1 imply that food entrepreneurs received formal schooling in hospitality management courses. Some are degree holders in the graduate school who took courage to put-up their business coming from their own personal funds. These entrepreneurs attended training related to food preparation and processing to assure the safety of the prepared food to its customers. The study of Avermaete et al. (2004) highlighted the key role of the skills of the workforce, the firm's investment in know-how and the use of external sources of information. There is, however, no evidence of a significant relationship between the characteristics of the entrepreneur and the firm's innovation performance. Baş et al. (2007) said that the majority of entrepreneurs identified improved customer confidence as a benefit of implementing a food safety management system. Lack of knowledge about food procedures and other food safety programs were identified as the main barriers for food safety in food businesses. Jacxsens et al. (2010) stated that food businesses which evaluate the

performance of their food safety management system in a more structured way and according to very strict and specific criteria will have a better insight in their actual microbiological food safety performance, because food safety problems will be more systematically detected. The diagnosis can be a useful tool to have a first indication about the microbiological performance of a food safety management system present in the food business.

Motarjemi and Käferstein (1999) presented the reasons for the increase in foodborne diseases, the role that the hazard analysis and critical control point system plays in preventing foodborne diseases, the determinants of its success and failure, and the contribution, which can reasonably be expected from the implementation to customers' health. Yapp and Fairman (2006) assessed the factors affecting compliance with food safety legislation within small and medium-sized food businesses. Their study showed that whilst some of the barriers identified within other research were present within food businesses (specifically time and money), there were also a number of complex, underlying issues that prevented compliance with regulatory requirements and which have implications for regulatory and enforcement policy. These barriers included a lack of trust in food safety legislation and enforcement officers; a lack of motivation in dealing with food safety legislation; and a lack of knowledge and understanding.

Entrepreneurs' Competencies Based on Experiences

Tables 2 to 5 present the competencies based on the experiences of the successful entrepreneurs in terms of their leadership, innovativeness, technical, and behavioral attributes.

Table 2
Entrepreneurs' Competency on Leadership

INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Able to communicate customers and staff	2.76	Very Useful	1
Able to motivate	2.73	Very Useful	2
Pursue tasks and issues until results are achieved	2.72	Very Useful	3
Trustworthy	2.70	Very Useful	4
Resourceful	2.68	Very Useful	5
Honest and sound leader	2.64	Very Useful	6.5
Get things done	2.64	Very Useful	6.5
See opportunities rather than obstacles	2.61	Very Useful	8.5
Committed to mission	2.61	Very Useful	8.5
Able to work with others	2.59	Very Useful	10
Persistent	2.58	Very Useful	11.5
Able to listen for improvement	2.58	Very Useful	11.5
Multi-task by choice	2.56	Very Useful	13.5
Charismatic	2.56	Very Useful	13.5
Flexible	2.54	Very Useful	15.5
Ask for advice when needed	2.54	Very Useful	15.5
The first person to speak-up	2.52	Very Useful	17
Focused on achieving goals	2.45	Very Useful	18
Team player	2.44	Very Useful	19.5
Patient	2.44	Very Useful	19.5
Strategic thinker	2.36	Very Useful	21.5
Happy to take the lead	2.36	Very Useful	21.5
Achievement orientated	2.22	Moderately Useful	23
Visionary	2.17	Moderately Useful	24
Risk-taker	2.16	Moderately Useful	25
Sub Mean	2.53	Very Useful	

Table 2 shows that the indicators, “able to communicate customers and staff” ranked 1, “able to motivate” ranked 2, and “pursue tasks and issues until results are achieved” ranks 3. The results reveal that entrepreneurs should know how to converse his ideas to his staff and to his customers by means of oral and written communication.

Cohn and Friedman (2002) provide many insights as to how employers ought to manage human resources. Issues discussed include employee theft, motivation (providing an honest day’s work and providing employees with meaningful and dignified work), compensation (paying wages on time), providing benefits for employees, and ethics in negotiations.

Table 3 presents the competency of the entrepreneurs in terms of innovativeness.

Table 3
Entrepreneurs’ Competency on Innovativeness

INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Likely to put off making difficult or important decisions	2.74	Very Useful	1
Solve problems creatively	2.66	Very Useful	2
Establish dependable resources where you can buy current, name brand and designer merchandise below wholesale prices	2.64	Very Useful	3
Provide food samples during happy hours	2.62	Very Useful	4
Look for better and new ways of doing things	2.56	Very Useful	5
Accept orders through the Web or mobile phones	2.46	Very Useful	6
Empower employees to make important decisions, even if it means losing a small amount of money to make your customers happy	2.40	Very Useful	7
Consider introducing fun ways to encourage increased dining during off times	2.39	Very Useful	8.5
Like change and the unexpected	2.39	Very Useful	8.5
Seek out challenges	2.35	Very Useful	10
Use a suggestion box and customer want slips	2.30	Moderately Useful	11
Involve employees in making suggestions for improving business and cutting costs	2.26	Moderately Useful	13
Use newsletters as a "marketing tool" to remind customers of the products or services you provide	2.26	Moderately Useful	13
Uses unique, imaginative, and cost-efficient ways to advertise a product	2.26	Moderately Useful	13
Implement a program to reward your employees for their extra efforts and innovative ideas	2.22	Moderately Useful	15.5
Offer a scoop of ice cream and greet them a birthday song	2.22	Moderately Useful	15.5
Attend trade shows that provide the latest technology, inventory systems, educational seminars, and other industry related resources	2.18	Moderately Useful	18
Create website for online advertisement	2.18	Moderately Useful	18
Join other stores like yours in area-wide buying programs to receive better prices or trade discounts	2.18	Moderately Useful	18
Offer food in package menu	2.10	Moderately Useful	20.5
Prefer to avoid taking risks	2.10	Moderately Useful	20.5
Believe that 'if something works it doesn't need changing	2.04	Moderately Useful	22
Join to trade associations and subscribe to newsletters and trade publications to keep you informed	1.96	Moderately Useful	23
Do cross-marketing by joining forces with restaurants, clubs, or whatever to jointly develop special promotions	1.86	Moderately Useful	24
Accept Visa, Mastercard, Discover, and American Express	1.60	Least Useful	25
Sub Mean	2.28	Moderately Useful	

Table 3 shows that the indicators, “Likely to put off making difficult or important decisions” ranked 1, “Solve problems creatively” ranked 2, and “Establish dependable resources where you can buy current, name brand and designer merchandise below wholesale prices” ranked 3. The data revealed that entrepreneurs should have know-how on decision-making in business procedures, policies and standards. Gellynck, Vermeire and Viaene (2007) stated that local food businesses demonstrate a stronger innovation competence and that businesses operating internationally benefit from regional networking. Businesses gain innovation competence by searching for external knowledge on different geographical scales. As these networks have the potential to enhance the innovation competence of firms, support to regional networking is promoted as a policy tool.

Pekovic and Galia (2009) investigated the impact of quality systems on innovation performance using the method of propensity matching. Results indicated that the innovation performance of firms with top quality level is higher than that of firms with medium quality level which is also higher than that of firms with low-quality level for certain areas of innovation. However, they found that the difference in innovation performance between firms with medium and low-quality Levels is not of a great magnitude. Their study implies that in order to achieve a significant innovation performance improvement via quality systems, a very well established quality system is needed within the firm.

Table 4 presents the competency of the entrepreneurs in terms of technical attributes.

Table 4
Entrepreneurs’ Technical Competency

INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Know what kind of equipment and technology is suitable for business	2.74	Very Useful	1
Know how to improve packaging of product	2.71	Very Useful	2
Enterprising in order to achieve significant results in business	2.65	Very Useful	3
Willingness to undertake any matters concerning the business	2.59	Very Useful	4
Enjoy routine and predictability	2.57	Very Useful	5
Get caught up in the details of things	2.55	Very Useful	6
Prefer full information before making a decision	2.49	Very Useful	7
Develop a new product using the same raw materials used	2.48	Very Useful	8
Know how to improve the way the product made	2.47	Very Useful	9
Look for regular reassurance	2.45	Very Useful	10
Know how to cost the product	2.44	Very Useful	11
Turn ideas into action	2.43	Very Useful	12
Know how to sell the product more successfully	2.40	Very Useful	13
Seek out responsibility	2.37	Very Useful	14
Choose good raw materials	2.36	Very Useful	15
Reduce waste and loss in raw materials	2.33	Moderately Useful	16
Know how much working capital is needed for business	2.32	Moderately Useful	17.5
Know how to go about applying for a loan	2.32	Moderately Useful	17.5
Need encouragement to achieve goals	2.29	Moderately Useful	19
Know how the product can keep longer	2.28	Moderately Useful	20
Discuss business difficulties and identify solutions with entrepreneurs who are in the same business	2.26	Moderately Useful	21
Know how to reduce operating costs and make more profit	2.24	Moderately Useful	22
Improve the product hygiene	2.20	Moderately Useful	23
Calculate the risk versus the reward of alternative options	2.14	Moderately Useful	24.5
Make a totally new product	2.14	Moderately Useful	24.5
Submean	2.41	Very Useful	

Table 4 shows that the indicators, “Know what kind of equipment and technology is suitable for business” ranked 1, “Know how to improve the packaging of product” ranked 2, and “Enterprising in order to achieve significant results in business” ranked 3. The table reveals that entrepreneurs should have know-how on the equipment, facilities and technologies used in his business. Panisello and Quantick (2001), said that technical barriers represent all those practice, attitudes and perceptions that negatively affect the understanding of food business concept. Zemke (2002) concluded that a good business model is critical, as is having the right resources, but that ultimately the human resource becomes the powerful make or break factor. Jevšnik et al. (2008) said that the importance of human resource management, as well as, employees’ work satisfaction is mostly neglected in the units of food supply chain. Some gaps of food handlers’ knowledge on microbiological hazards were found, especially for those working in catering and retail. Analysis of employees’ opinion toward food safety requirements has shown which hazards were ascribed as more important regard food safety.

Table 5 presents the competency of the entrepreneurs in terms of behavioral attributes. The table shows that the indicators, “Initiative” ranked 1, and “Ambitious and Persistent and don’t give up easily” were ranked 1. The table further revealed that entrepreneurs should be resourceful in finding ways and means on how to improve the business.

Table 5
Entrepreneurs’ Behavioral Competency

INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description	Rank
Initiative	2.66	Very Useful	1
Ambitious	2.64	Very Useful	2.5
Persistent and don't give-up easily	2.64	Very Useful	2.5
Believing the work you are doing will pay off	2.60	Very Useful	4.5
Systematic in planning	2.60	Very Useful	4.5
Self-confident	2.58	Very Useful	6
Self-motivated	2.53	Very Useful	7
Don't let obstacles get in the way of getting things done	2.50	Very Useful	8
Management of information	2.49	Very Useful	9
Problem solving	2.44	Very Useful	10
Tend to take the route of least resistance	2.39	Very Useful	11
Staying away from negativity	2.37	Very Useful	12
Prefer to do one thing at a time	2.34	Very Useful	13
Like being told what to do and what is expected	2.31	Moderately Useful	14
Perfectionist	2.24	Moderately Useful	15.5
Quality performance	2.24	Moderately Useful	15.5
See risk as a necessary part of life	2.22	Moderately Useful	17.5
Try to avoid criticism	2.22	Moderately Useful	17.5
Get on with things without being asked	2.20	Moderately Useful	19
Persuasion and influencing abilities	2.16	Moderately Useful	20
Tenacity	2.14	Moderately Useful	21
Take risk and manage it	2.12	Moderately Useful	22
Easily influenced by others’ opinions	2.10	Moderately Useful	23
Infatuated with what you do	2.08	Moderately Useful	24
Prefer to work alone	2.02	Moderately Useful	25
Sub Mean	2.35	Very Useful	

Baron (2007) stressed that entrepreneurs play a central role in new venture creation. Because they do, careful attention to relevant aspects of their behavior and cognition can offer useful insights into key aspects of this complex process. Evidence is reviewed concerning the role of behavioral and cognitive factors in several key activities performed by entrepreneurs. In addition, the potential role of a variable that

has not yet been systematically investigated in the context of new venture creation affect is explored. Wildes (2005) suggested that managers create a campaign to promote the positive attributes of work in the food service industry to help overcome employee attrition. It was also suggested that those who are high in stigma consciousness that also intend to stay in the restaurant industry be recruited as spokes-people for the industry.

Profile of the Company

Table 6 presents the profile of the companies in terms of type of business, product line, capitalization, years of operation, and the number of employees, as can be seen, most of the food businesses in Metropolitan Cebu are fast food type, and destination restaurants', sources of capitalization are from personal funds, operating for 1 to 3 years, and with having not more than 10 employees.

Table 6
Profile of the Company

Variable	f	%
Type of Business		
Casual dining	26	52.00
Fast food	19	38.00
Fine dining	5	10.00
Total	50	100
Product line		
Brasserie and bistro	2	4.00
Buffet and smorgasbord	6	12.00
Café	2	4.00
Cafeteria	7	14.00
Coffeehouse	2	4.00
Destination restaurant	12	24.00
Mongolian barbeque	8	16.00
Others	9	18.00
Total	50	100
Capitalization		
Personal funds	33	1
Family and friends	25	2
Financial institutions	20	3
Others	0	4
Total	50	100
Number of years of operation		
Less than a year	0	0.00
1 to 3 years	17	34.00
4 to 6 years	14	28.00
7 to 10 years	10	20.00
More than 10 years	9	18.00
Total	50	100
Number of employee		
Less than 10	28	56.00
10 to 30	18	36.00
31 to 50	1	2.00
51 to 100	0	0.00
More than 100	3	6.00
Total	50	100

Data on Table 6 imply that food businesses operating within Metropolitan Cebu are varied in nature addressing the need of the residents and foreign visitors.

Cebu as a preferred tourist destination should cater to the food preferences of these visitors in order to give satisfaction while staying in Cebu.

Huddleston et al. (2004) revealed that in the intensely competitive food industry, increasing and sustaining repeat buying behavior among store customers can significantly increase profits. Pronk and Kottke (2009) say that food business should represent a powerful stakeholder group that should leverage its influence on health choice initiatives designed to create supportive environments. Furthermore, Ahmed, Ahmed and Salman (2005) mentioned that food products require the general marketing approaches and techniques applied to the marketing of other kinds of products and services. In addition, for the food industry to improve further, it needs to adopt the best practices in the business arena. Businesses that are the most progressive in the management of the supply chain are expected to be the most successful and profitable.

Test for Significant Relationship

The study hypothesized that there was no significant relationship between profile of the entrepreneurs and their competencies standards based on their experiences. Results of the statistical analysis can be seen in Table 7

Table 7
Relationship between Profile and Competency Standards

	Computed r value	Sequence Correlation	Computed t value	Critical t value	Interpretation	Decision on HO
Relationship between Competency Standards and						
Age	-0.15	Little negative	-1.054	2.011	Not Significant	Accept
Gender	0.01	Little positive	0.036	2.011	Not Significant	Accept
Educational Qualification	-0.10	Little negative	-0.716	2.011	Not Significant	Accept
Other Trainings	-0.04	Little negative	-0.300	2.011	Not Significant	Accept

The results indicate the acceptance of the null hypothesis which says that the profiles of the respondents do not have significant relationship with the competencies as experienced by the successful entrepreneurs. The computed t-values are all less than the critical t-values of 2.011 at 0.05 level of significance and df of 48. When the respondents were asked how many times they succeeded or failed in their business ventures, 60% said they of them failed once, 25% failed twice, and 5% failed thrice, while another 5% of them never experienced failure. These proved that there is no shortcut procedure to any business success.

Salient Points from Interview

Additional data through follow-up interviews from the food entrepreneurs were gathered. Most of the respondents own their food business through their personal funds. They have ample experiences that made them decide to put up a food business. These food entrepreneurs encountered financial difficulty during the first three years of their companies' existence. Food sales were not as good as expected considering that the market are not properly introduced to customers. As observed during the interview, some businesses do not have seats for customers. Most are stalls where customers will just stand while waiting for the food to be served.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This section restates the purpose of the study, summarizes the major findings gathered, states the general conclusions and lists down the appropriate recommendations. The research environment of the study was the food businesses in the Metropolitan Cebu and were owned and operated by the graduates of the different higher education institutions. In this study, the descriptive-survey method of research was used. The research participants of the study were the graduates of the different colleges and universities in the province of Cebu during the year 1980 to present. These food entrepreneurs were used as respondents of the study wherein they answered the two sets of researcher-made questionnaires. These questionnaires were utilized to gather profile of the respondents and their entrepreneurial competencies as experienced by them.

Summary of Findings

- Profile of the entrepreneurs. The study shows that most of the respondents' are 32 years or older, female and holders of baccalaureate degree. The entrepreneurs have attended trainings on food safety, food and water microbiology, food labeling, sanitation standard operating procedures, safety and risk assessment, and food safety and law procedures.
- Entrepreneurs' competencies in leadership the top 3 attributes were: able to communicate with customers and staff; able to motivate; and pursue tasks and issues until results are achieved.
- Entrepreneurs' innovativeness competencies in innovativeness the top 3 attributes were: likely to put off making difficult or important decisions; solve problems creatively; and establish dependable resources where one can buy current, name brand and designer merchandise below wholesale prices.
- Technical competencies, the top 3 attributes were: know what kind of equipment and technology is suitable for business; know how to improve the packaging of product; and enterprising in order to achieve significant results in business.
- Behavioral competencies the top 3 attributes indicators were: initiative; ambitious; and persistent and don't give up easily.
- Most company profile of the food businesses in Metropolitan Cebu are fast food type, destination restaurants, with sources of capitalization from personal funds, had been operating for 1 to 3 years, and with not more than 10 employees.
- Relationship of Respondents Profile of Entrepreneurial Competencies. Profile of the respondents do not have significant relationships with their competencies based on their own experiences.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following can be concluded:

1. The concept of entrepreneurial competencies of HRM graduates plays a powerful construct for entrepreneurship education, training, and practice.
2. The added value of focusing on competence in entrepreneurship education and training lies in making the small food businesses' owner aware of the importance of certain entrepreneurial competencies and in providing direction for competence development to future HRM graduates.
3. No significant relationship existed between the respondents demographic profile and their entrepreneurial competencies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are thought to be of value:

1. The current curriculum of HRM should be reviewed and re-engineered to address the emerging needs of the region, as well as, to address in the preparation for ASEAN 2015.
2. A specialized major for Food Entrepreneurship in the BSHRM could be offered in order to cater to the demands of the increasing population in Cebu City.
3. It is also recommended that the proposed OBE Course Guide for Food Entrepreneurship be used in the College of Hotel and Restaurant Management, University of Cebu as a medium in proposing for an additional curriculum in Food Entrepreneurship. Through the prepared course modules, outlines, and its objectives, it would be easier for the implementer to deploy the program for food entrepreneurship.

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